

Single chip-based digital oscilloscope for remote education

Version 1

Description

The aim of the project – is to design an entire oscilloscope as well as a signal generator into a single integrated circuit (IC), making the cost very low (for large quantities) and, therefore, affordable for each electronics student.

During the project, new knowledge will be created and deposited in an open database. This knowledge will be from the project's specifics: digital IP, analogue circuit schematics and scientific articles.

Digital IP will be written in VHDL. Expected IP:

- VGA interface
- HDMI interface
- I2C interface
- Oscilloscope interface design with VHDL code.

In the analogue part, schematic solutions adapted for integration into a chip are presented:

- Analog - digital converter schematic solutions.
- Sample and hold
- Comparator schematics
- Amplifier schematics.
- Final chip schematic

The project also includes publications, and depending on the publisher, they will or will not be deposited here.

P2.1. Mathematical modelling of ADC for different topologies.

P2.2. Survey of ADCs.

P3.1. Prototyping Oscilloscope on a chip. Preliminary results.

P3.2. High-speed ADC for an oscilloscope.

- P3.3. Oscilloscope on the chip. Preliminary results.
P3.4. Oscilloscope on the chip. (Final results).
P3.5. Possible application of oscilloscope on the chip.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Izp-2024/1-0442

Researchers

Maris Terauds (0000-0001-6934-0036), Vladimirs Smolaninovs (0009-0007-1703-6754), Pauls Eriks Sics (0009-0009-6615-9173), John Liobe (0000-0001-7268-5991)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Single chip-based digital oscilloscope for remote education](#)

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Organizations:

Riga Technical University

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: lzp-2024/1-0442

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2027-01-31

4. Templates

Descriptions

Oscilloscope interface design with VHDL code

This code will draw oscilloscope interface on separate connected monitor. Drawing made with VHDL code.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Te tiks publicēti kodi kas apraksta ciparu daļas no oscilloscopa.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Programme source code

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- Others

Here will be expected folder with separate txt files, probably we will archive it

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

For FGPA programmer. To reuse this data set.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

FPGA scope interface VHDL

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

3 years till 31.12.2027

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Quartus Prime

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Academic Free License 3.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Maris Terauds (0000-0001-6934-0036)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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